

DataTools4Heart: Instructions for the qualitative evaluation of Named Entity Recognition Systems (MS16)

Introduction

In the context of the DataTools4Heart project, different Named Entity Recognition systems have been created to extract information related to diseases, symptoms, procedures and medications from cardiology texts. As part of Milestone 16 (MS16), we need to verify the performance of these models. One way in which we will do this is by performing an analysis and qualitative evaluation of different models in each language over a selected group of texts with the help of the project's clinicians. This document describes the instructions that the clinicians must follow to perform this evaluation.

The task itself is quite simple and intuitive. You will be provided with a set of documents annotated using two different systems. One is a baseline system, a basic extractor based on rules and a dictionary which uses only the resources that were available at the very start of the project. The other is a more advanced Transformers-based system (i.e. neural network-based) that has been trained using the annotated corpora generated as part of the project. You need to look at the results of each system using the annotation tool brat as a document viewer, paying attention to various aspects that are described in this document, and then fill in one questionnaire for each system (so, two questionnaires total).

The texts you will be looking at come from two different sources. Some of them are part of the ParaClite corpus, artificial hospital records created for the project in each language and manually translated into the other languages of the project. These were chosen due to their

thematic and structural similarity to the actual hospital records the systems will be ultimately applied to. A smaller subset of documents come from a published corpus of anonymized cardiology discharge letters, originally written in Greek and machine translated into DataTools4Heart's languages. These were used as part of the ELCardioCC 2025 Shared Task¹, focused on automatic clinical coding, and have been chosen so that we could test the system on actual hospital records during this stage of the project. In total, we are asking you to revise 20 documents: 14 from ParaClite (2 originally written in your language and 12 manually translated into it from the other consortium languages) and 6 from ELCardioCC.

If you are having any problems or questions with the task, please don't hesitate to contact Fernando Gallego-Donoso (fgallegodonoso@gmail.com) and Salvador Lima-López (salvador.limalopez@gmail.com) from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

Thanks a lot for taking the time to participate in the task, we really appreciate it!

Task Instructions

Please follow this procedure in order to perform the qualitative evaluation:

1. Start by reading the entire questionnaire and make sure you understand it.
 - Both questionnaires are the same, so you don't need to read both! The only difference between them is that one is meant to be used for the baseline system and the other for the Transformers-based system.
 - The questions and their purpose are explained in this document.
 - If there is something you are not completely sure about, please contact Fernando and Salva so that they can help you.
2. Next, open the spreadsheet with the links to the documents to review.
 - At the bottom of the screen there are different tabs, one for each language. Please choose your language's tab.
 - In the spreadsheet, you have the option to see, for each document, the annotations of only the baseline system, the annotations of only the

¹ Dimitriadis, Dimitris, Vasiliki Patsiou, Eleonora Stoikopoulou, Achilleas Toumpas, Alkis Kipouros, D. Papadopoulos, A. Bekiaridou et al. "Overview of ELCardioCC task on clinical coding in cardiology at BioASQ 2025." In *CLEF*. 2025.

Transformers-based system, or both at the same time using brat's side-by-side view. For this task, we'll mainly use the side-by-side view.

- Remember that you can move between documents in brat using the left and right arrows in your keyboard. You don't need to open each document separately.
3. Now, open the very first document using the side-by-side view link.
- The left side corresponds to the baseline system's output. The right side corresponds to the Transformers-based system's output.
 - Read through the document focusing on the baseline system's annotations, then move on to the Transformers-based system's annotations when you are filling the second questionnaire.
 - The next steps will go through the basic methodology you should follow to analyze the documents. Do them first for the baseline system, then for the Transformers-based system.
4. Questions 1 to 6 are about you and your background.
- Complete the questions with your name and surname, clinical site and native/spoken languages.
5. Questions 7 to 14 are about your first impressions of the system.
- At this step we want to learn about what you think about the system at a first glance, without getting too much into the details of possible errors.
 - In order to do this, please rate your impression using the provided options, which are graded from "Very well" to "Very bad results".
 - Question 7 is about your general impression of the full results; questions 8 to 12 ask about specific entity types.
 - Finally, questions 13 and 14 are free-text fields where you can express your opinion about the strengths (question 13) and weaknesses (question 14) of the evaluated system.
6. Questions 15 to 22 ask you to think more critically about the system's output.
- These questions describe various possible error types and ask you to confirm whether they appear in the documents or not. Some possible cases are given for each error type – check them ONLY if you have seen them in the documents.

- If you notice a different case related to one of the error types not covered by our suggestions, feel free to write it using the “Other” field in each question.
- Questions 15 to 18 are about the general error types that you may find:
 - Question 15 is about boundary errors. Boundary errors are those related to the extension of the entities that the system did predict (e.g. an entity is too short, too long, split in multiple parts, ...).
 - Question 16 is about errors in the predicted label. Sometimes, you might not agree with the label given by the system to a predicted entity. Keep in mind that some of these cases might be related to how the labels are defined in the annotation guidelines (e.g. medication family names are annotated as procedures, only specific medication names are labelled as medications).
 - Question 17 is about missing predictions. The systems might have sometimes not predicted clinical entities that you think should be covered by one of our labels.
 - Question 18 is about incorrect predictions. The systems might have predicted things that are completely incorrect for different reasons.
- Questions 19 to 21 ask about specific causes of the errors you may have found:
 - Question 19 is about errors related to ambiguity and context. Some errors might come from abbreviations not being understood correctly by the system or it missing variations of the same clinical concept.
 - Question 20 is about errors related to formatting and tokenization (word segmentation). For instance, some mentions might include unwanted punctuation.
 - Question 21 is about errors related to clinical aspects and clinical terminology.
- Finally, question 22 is another free-text field where you can write a more in-depth comment of the system after having performed a more critical analysis during this step.

7. Questions 23 to 27 are your final assessment of the system.

- Similarly to the set of questions about your first impression, you’ll need to rate both the complete set of predictions as well as the four individual labels.

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- This time, use a 0-10 scale to rate the systems. 0 means that the systems are completely non-functional, while 10 means that they work perfectly with no errors.
8. That's all! You can now send your results.
- If you have done the questionnaire for the baseline system, please move on to the Transformers-based system.
 - Thank you again for your time!